

ImpactOS: Open Science Impact Reporter

Professional background: I am MetaDocencia's Board Chair and Impact Measurement Lead, driving initiatives to advance Open Science (OS) in Latin America. As a tenured researcher at the National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET) in Argentina, I have extensive experience in promoting OS practices and addressing the challenges of working openly within institutional frameworks. I co-lead MetaDocencia+NASA's "Teaching TOPS OpenCore by Embedding Community Values" grant and the R programming training at the University of Buenos Aires for cognitive psychology researchers. As an R-Ladies organizer, and certified instructor for The Carpentries and RStudio (now Posit), I empower researchers to integrate open, reproducible data science methods into their work. My commitment has been recognized by NumFOCUS DISC Unconf 2023, Posit Conf 2024, and KHIPU 2025 - Latin American Meeting in Artificial Intelligence, where I was invited to participate through competitive selections.

The problem: Despite growing global interest in OS, scientists and organizations struggle to communicate their impact effectively. OS impact often centers on publications, neglecting practices like open resource development, community projects, and training. These activities are critical for transforming research practices but are rarely recognized in institutional evaluations, which discourages researchers from adopting them. Moreover, the scattered nature of OS metrics combined with the absence of unified monitoring tools, exacerbates the challenge of consolidating and interpreting contributions. At the same time, existing tools frequently require technical expertise and remain proprietary, creating additional barriers for groups with limited resources to hire specialized personnel.

Proposed idea: This challenge can be addressed by developing ImpactOS, an open source platform that assists research teams and organizations in generating reports that measure and communicate their contributions to OS practices. ImpactOS will offer tailored templates, automate reporting, and suggest metrics by discipline. It will include text analysis tools to review institutional documents, reports, and publications to benchmark OS activities over time and extract qualitative insights from case studies, testimonials, or media mentions. A key goal of ImpactOS is to broaden the scope of OS monitoring, accounting for diverse practices such as participatory processes, changes in research and publishing methodologies, and contributions to societal values like equity and diversity. Additionally, it will measure how well-connected a community and individuals are and how critical they are in bridging those who are not connected yet. In that sense, this project will synergize with Nicolás Palopoli's proposal to develop a global map of OS and an associated common vocabulary. Ultimately, ImpactOS seeks to make OS contributions more visible, promote their recognition in institutional evaluations, and foster the adoption of open research practices globally. **I am flexible and willing to collaboratively shape this idea.**

Landscape of other solutions: Initiatives such as Open Science Monitor (European Commission) or PLOS Open Science Indicators track trends in open access, collaborative research, and transparency across countries and disciplines but only focus on quantitative data and lack the granularity needed for organizational-level insights. Altmetric, a proprietary platform, tracks attention to individual outputs, such as a publication or dataset, focusing on how often they are mentioned in news outlets, blogs, social media, or policy documents. It does not apply to broader organizational contributions or OS practices and it measures mentions rather than implementation.

My skills and gaps: I actively participate in communities focused on OS and engage in discussions about diverse metrics for monitoring its adoption, including contributions to UNESCO-led groups on the subject. My expertise includes data collection, curation, analysis, and the generation of accessible and comprehensive reports. While I have substantial experience in programming with R, I am less familiar with developing software and deploying it into production. However, I bring valuable complementary strengths, such as a deep understanding of OS principles, proficiency in synthesizing complex data into actionable insights, and effective collaboration with multidisciplinary teams. I collaborate closely with MetaDocencia's team, with experience in developing open-source tools, interoperable platforms, open infrastructure, and aligning licensing with OS principles.

Quarterly milestones:

- Q1: Documentation of functional and technical requirements, initial UI/UX prototype, and detailed development roadmap.
- Q2: Functional MVP, backend connected to at least one external repository (e.g., Zenodo, Dryad), basic interface for creating and exporting reports.
- Q3. Pilot platform with advanced features, reports based on qualitative analysis, and large language model metrics.
- Q4. Pilot platform in production and publicly accessible, documentation. Business plan.

Budget: (hidden.)

Work location: remote.